

Hippasa holmerae Thorell (Araneae: Lycosidae): a new predator of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers

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Hippasa holmerae Thorell, a lycosid spider, inhabits dryland areas such as earthen embankments of irrigation canals or reservoirs near paddy fields in the Philippines. It seeks shelter in soil crevices and actively moves over the water surface in search of prey on rice plants. When caged on rice plants infested with brown and whitebacked planthoppers or green leafhoppers, the spider readily preys on those species. It also was observed to prey on two species of legume insect pests grown after rice: *Amrasca biguttula* (Shiraki) and *Ophiomyia phaseoli* (Tyron). The adult spider can readily be distinguished from other paddy field lycosids by the slightly procurved anterior and strongly recurved posterior eyes; the presence of three promarginal and retromarginal teeth on the chelicerae; brown legs and cephalothorax: slant posterior region of the carapace; longitudinal black band on the midsternum; brown cardiac area on the dorsum of the dark brown abdomen; and large posterior spinnerets, which are twice the length of those in the anterior position (see figure). *Hippasa holmerae* is a new item for the Philippines and Asian checklist of spiders inhabiting rice fields

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